

Impact of Natural Disasters on Common Man – A Case Study of Coorg District (Karnataka)

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Abstract

Natural disasters can take place anytime, anywhere in this universe. When disasters happen, it would totally damage the entire living system, make life complicated, and impose formidable challenges on human community. When one is having total comforts in all walks of life & life is moving smooth & cozier, people feel like distracting the natural eco systems, natural resources for their economic gain. This will lead to sudden climatic change & this change will in turn bring about worst out of worst situation to human beings, where meeting even the basic needs become difficult & one has to totally rely on others, come across with fervent appeal to the government, social service activists, natural donors etc. These people have to come up with a helping hand to the victims who have miserably suffered due to this natural disaster that took place all of sudden.

Coorg is a chilled place called as Kashmir of Karnataka, lies in Western Ghats. The entire geography of this region is occupied by valleys, rivers, streams, paddy fields & coffee estates. Moreover tourism is one of the pre occupied business which is rapidly taking place here from more than two decades. Home stays with comfortable hospitality, natural presence & served with traditional foods attracts tourists across the entire nation as well as outside. Many people directly or indirectly make their living on either tourism or by agriculture. Presently due to this natural calamity, normal living is completely disturbed. People who are well off economically are forcefully thrown in the streets & their condition has become pathetic. This study completely try to throw light on the same & to the maximum possible extent try to cover about the measures that has been taken up till date & the plans to be implemented in future to bring the situation to normal level & help out the victims.

Keywords: Disasters, Formidable, Distracting, Fervent & Pathetic.

Introduction

A Natural disaster is a consequence of artificial activities undertaken by man for his economic gain. The result of this will have negative impact on all the resources of our earth, increased human activities have to bear financial, structural & human losses. The resulting loss depends on the capacity of the population to support or resist the disaster. In other words, disasters occur when hazards meet vulnerability. A disaster is not possible without human involvement. The degree of potential loss depends on the nature of hazard itself. Loss taken place in coorg district of Karnataka was because of torrential rainfall & landslides in some of the Western Ghats & the hilly regions, areas tremendously surrounded by mountains & forests. This disaster has created a worst situation & came out with the potential event

that had a wide effect on the people. The incident occurred abruptly resulting in a torrential rainfall which involved destroying out actual elements on the ground surface, including rocks, trees, parts of houses, cattle & livestock's, poultry, & even estate & fields of many farmers & agriculturists who are the part of the geography & contribute something to our economic development. These elements were clearly swept out in the rains. One more aspect considered to be the cause of this is the general instability in the surrounding land, mudslides/mudflows due to heavy rains caused loose soil on steep terrain collapse & slide downwards. Prolonged rainfall resulted in rivers & streams overflowing swelled from excessive precipitation upstream & caused wide spread damage to areas downstream.

Coorg in Karnataka was considered as one of the safest place where people come for outing, site seeing, tourism, and pilgrimage & relaxation purposes. Since climate is very much chilled it welcomed much of tourists from outside. This developed tourism lodging & home stay markets. Home stays worked out to a certain manner & many people took undue advantage of the same. Coorg has over the years witnessed declining rate of natural elements & resources, increasing population density due to outside migration & more environmental problems due to rapidly growing human activities. One of this had totally led to natural disaster which took place this year (2018) itself.

Causes for Natural Disaster in coorg

Following are the observed causes which are considered very likely as far as natural disaster is concerned.

1. Increasing deforestation.
2. Higher number of construction activities even at unpermitted areas.
3. Increase in the number of Home stays (Unpermitted).
4. Digging more bore wells than necessary to provide water resources to growing population.
5. Mindset of people turning completely commercial.
6. Increasing mining & quarry activities.
7. Torrential rainfall causing landslides, loss of property & lives.
8. Illegal sand extraction beyond the permit limits (Sand Mafia) & transporting the same to other parts.
9. Soft soil (Clay) quality which could easily come out when there is continuous rain water flow causing mudslide.

Impact of Natural Disaster Observed for Common Man

Natural hazard has brought about abrupt changes in the lives of people. Unexpected events changed lifestyle of people, many wanted to make themselves commercialized with the naturally arise beauty. The following is the impact that has been deeply observed as far as the current years disaster is concerned.

1. Rivers, lakes, ponds, started overflowing causing destruction to plants, trees, animals & other resources.
2. Peaks & Mountains of north coorg (Mercara & its surroundings) were badly affected. This has resulted in landslides. Local landslides destroyed much of the resources & deteriorated financial position of masses as well as making wealthier impoverished.
3. Essential commodities was not available on time due to transit blocks (Transportation difficulties)
4. Deeper loss of precious lives & property. Innocent people were carried away by water & were found missing.
5. Loss of innocent animals, cattle, poultry, etc. which is directly presumed as economic loss for the owners.
6. Major roads, Highways etc. connecting routes between the cities had lost their identity, most of the transports were cancelled as roads itself were carried away by water.
7. Public & goods transport systems had to ply on alternate routes & most of them were associated from out of the district. Travelling through alternate routes increased travelling time & cost. Third parties started taking undue advantage of the situation by demanding double fares.

8. Complete destruction of cut roads & heavy traffic on alternate roads.
9. Wage earners, Micro enterprise owners, tour & travel operators, etc. were badly hit.
10. Government started food service centers for the victims with the help of NGO's & local volunteers for serving food to the victims. Many donors & esteemed people had to donate their offerings in monetary & non-monetary forms to meet the needs & requirements of those victims attacked by disaster. The intention of this scheme was to make victims feel comfortable & supply the necessary items.
11. Millionaires & Billionaires who were dominating & ruling the markets were totally injured physically & mentally. In a single week many were on to the streets forgetting their prosperity.
12. Governments financial as well as supportive aids provided did not reach the masses who were really affected by the disaster, but went out to the wrong hands who took undue advantage of this situation. Favoritism, linguistic politics, internal adjustments between themselves, discrimination of people based on local caste & outside has been observed & were reported directly by the local state based TV channels.
13. Most of the victims lost their nearest & dearest ones, property & assets. But some of them were protected by the rescue operations carried out by military team, police & local volunteer service teams.
14. Business, employment, local trade overall were desperately affected & many of the experts were of the opinion that coorg has gone twenty years back in its growth & development. In other words Market potential that currently existed has totally diminished, growth rate has slowed down & the affected areas would take couple of decades to come back to the former position.

Review of Literature

Literature is taken from leading newspapers & other published sources. Reviews are taken up to bridge the gap between the present study & earlier undertaken studies.

1. According to Anaya Vasudeva most of the sudden disasters even made many of them failed to locate their own houses. Heavy rains have built up water levels & increased force washed away even their cattle's too.
2. According to Dr DM Vinutha landslides took place due to loose soil at coorg district. Rocks surrounded by them had huge amount of granites & gneiss which are fragile & has comparatively lesser strength. due to heavy rainfall land from top surface muds started coming out to the lower surfaces & resulted in landslides.
3. According to Nataraja, economic activities majorly carried out at rural parts of northern coorg got affected. Economic activities majorly included home stay & estate stay. Most of them made up their home stay by destroying the nature & with highly commercial intentions.
4. According to Aleem Ahmed increased construction activities has brought about with demand for building materials. Therefore most of them started up with mining & quarry works to meet the demand for materials. These works have considerably reduced the strength of the soil & support to the trees.
5. According to DR Udayan governments developmental action plans to start a power house or power lines between Mysore & Calicut proved very much expensive by causing destruction of wide range of thick forests. More than 55000 trees were fallen down for the purpose of this project. Also planning of railway lines between Mysore & Cananore also forcibly led to cut down of wide variety of trees. The budget imposed by the government was 5287 crore rupees.
6. According to Vanajakshi, in the banks of river payaswini houses & commercial structures were constructed, this had increased pressures on catchment areas resulting in sliding of mountains national highways have subsided almost to a depth of 60 feet. Research study undertaken has proved that 17.04% of the area falls under extreme flooding zone & 11.52% is at very risky zone. Hence these projects undertaken have proved to be very risky & costly.

7. According to C R Das It will take a minimum years' time to recover or reconstruct coorg back. Firstly metal bridges have to be constructed entire districts infrastructure which is totally shattered into pieces should be reconstructed. Everyone should compulsorily learn a lesson to respect nature.

Statement of Problem

Coorg has witnessed a natural disaster which was earlier experienced around 90 years back. Naturally disaster has slowed down growth, destroyed property, assets and people. Location experiencing better prospects was turned down into isolated one. Most of the people who are enthusiastic, self-dependent, self-reliant have become miserably dependent on others. Best place has turned out to be bed lam place. Natural disaster has deeply affected transport, connectivity, mobility, trade & commerce. Even it has deeply affected traders, enterprise owners, agriculturists, farmers in their mundane activities. Natural disaster has also reduced tourist folk arrival in the district& has strongly installed panic among the people on safety & security of people. Stronger people have turned out to be weaker in the eyes of situation that has resulted due to natural disaster.

Objectives of the Study

Following objectives are expected to be met in this study, these are as follows.

1. To understand the impact of natural disaster on common man.
2. To study the responses of the victims who have suffered from this natural disaster.
3. To understand the measures taken up by concerned authorities for managing this disaster.
4. To give suggestions based on the observations of study.

Methodology Used in this Study

This study is basically incidental in nature, based on the recent disaster experienced at North Coorg in Karnataka. It is observed that landslides due to heavy torrential rains had negatively impacted the people living at that vicinity. Data for undertaking this study is extracted from both primary & secondary sources. Primary data is collected using observation & personal interview methods. Secondary data is collected from references of information's extracted from books, journals, related sites & related TV channels etc.

Since this study is based on practical incident that recently took place at coorg, information is more based on responses of respondents (Victims of disaster) . Statistical & numerical tools are not used due to the nature of data obtained from the respondents. Respondents chosen in this study are common persons who include household members, agriculturists, farmers, small street vendors, wage laborers, home stay & lodge owners etc. Number of respondents met & interviewed in this study is one hundred respondents. Responses given by them are recorded immediately& taken into consideration. Area chosen for the study is northern part of coorg district in Karnataka state which include Madenad, Jodupala, Devarakolli, Katakari, Hattihole, Makkandur, Boikeri, suntikoppa & Mercara town limits.

Scope & Significance of Study

Natural disasters such as landslides, destructions caused through heavy rainfall can cause imbalances in normal lives. From economic point of view, it disturbs normal economic activities , causes disequilibrium in normal trade & commerce activities. In the present situations it is clearly observed that tourism is worst affected at Kashmir of Karnataka. After this incident home & estate stays are banned. Most of the agricultural lands & estates, sources of income & revenue got affected. People from all aspects & professions suffered directly or indirectly. Growth rate of the geographical area witnessed a downturn. When these aspects are observed directly & reports given by the scientists are considered it has become very much evident to maintain the balance in our nature by taking care of our eco systems well. Not going against the rules & regulations imposed by the concerned departments for the wellbeing & safety of the people which can surely

come out with positive changes in the coming generations. Awareness level has to be spread positively without harming the sentiments of people, without disturbing the normal lives, without affecting permitted (By concerned officials) economic activities. This is the very important need of the hour, that cause & effect of these disasters need to be studied in detail & concrete steps to be taken up to avoid the same taking place in the future to the maximum possible extent. Important point to be noted & considered here is that if natural disaster takes place at full fledge it can put an end to all creatures including human beings & its effects will be disastrous.

Important Findings & Suggestions

Findings are given out from the responses given from the local respondents who were directly or indirectly the victims of this disaster. The major findings extracted are as follows.

1. Root cause for this disaster was illegal human activity, which included excess construction activities, deforestation, conversion of agricultural lands into residential & commercial plots for economic gain, running unauthorized, unpermitted home stays where all kinds of unlawful activities were likely possible.
2. Impact of this disaster was very much severe & this has led to disturbance to common lives, drastic drop in trade & commerce activities etc.
3. Tourism, home & estate stays have drastically affected & is presently banned for time being.
4. Reduction in the scope of direct & indirect employments & income levels.
5. Increased dependency on others. This has created huge income inequalities. Most of the rich people including enterprise owners, agriculturists lost their land, property & wealth are today are pleading to the government for financial relief measures.
6. Financial relief measures have not reached the right people. Lot of discrepancies have been heard & reported by the respondents regarding settlement of relief fund amount released from prime ministers & chief minister's relief funds.
7. Discrimination was observed in settlement of relief measures based on caste, creed & linguistic differences. No human beings were treated as equals. Favoritism is very much observed & reported in the renowned media channels live on the incidents took place.
8. Transportation of goods & services & passengers got severally affected. Government runs minimum number of buses & is always jam packed.
9. Schools, colleges, educational institutions got affected & were shut down close to two months.
10. Small wage earners, businessmen etc. suffered from un employment & lack of source of income. Some of the business enterprise owners experienced their business places getting completely washed away with flood or got destroyed by wind & heavy flow of water.
11. Overall diminished growth rate observed & it will take couple of decades to recover back to the same position.

Suggestive Measures

Following suggestive measures may be worthwhile if implemented at the earliest.

1. Natural reserve forests should not be misused for timber & other commercial purposes.
2. Construction activities should take place only with permissible limits & not exceeding the specified limits.
3. Illegal sand mafia, mining & quarry should be stopped as it may reduce the strength of the soil & also may be the root cause for land slide.
4. Unauthorized home stays should be checked again & again, strict action must be initiated against those who run the same.

5. Usage of plastics, plastic items, glass, and glass items should be minimized. It would be better if the same is banned & alternatives are encouraged for the same.
6. Plastics should not be dumped in wells, lakes, ponds, streams & rivers. This is because it will get blocked & will cause direct pollution.
7. Encouraging afforestation & trying to increase forest cover. Compulsory planting of plant & trees has to be made by every citizen. This will bring timely rainfall & reduces temperature.
8. Audit of finance of relief funds should take place meticulously & at surprise. Financial scams if found on the same should be severely punished.

Conclusion

Natural disasters can prove to be dangerous if it goes uncontrolled or turns wild. It can cause wide destruction to our plants, animals' natural resources & to humanity. Common causes responsible for natural disasters in coorg are human negligence, deforestation, running unauthorized home stays, and increased construction activities in unpermitted areas etc. awareness programs indicating warning signals on ill effects of disasters on humanity should be made from time to time with an integral component of sustainable development with a goal of reducing human, economic & environmental losses due to the hazards of all kinds. Another important aspect to be immediately considered is to chalk out a detailed plan of action keeping geographical conditions of this regions (Coorg) in mind which takes care of sensitive areas & try to implement the same at the earliest.

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